

The Planck Constant and Prime Curvatures – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants equation in its first and second representations, i.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and spin, it is possible to intersect it with Max Planck and Einstein Work on the Quantum oscillator being able to receive or emit discrete amount of energy. In addition to reasoning why $\alpha = 1/2$.

Introduction

In the 20-th century Max Planck discovered that matter can receive and emit, and therefore change only in discrete amounts. Such an idea as you know led to the discovery of the Planck constant which since then has been used all over the spectra of modern physics.

$$E = \hbar\omega \quad (1)$$

Later Einstein and Stern discovered in 1913, something just as amazing. Max Planck and the rest of the gang thought and $\alpha = 0$ but as it was discovered it was equal to one-half.

$$E = (n - \alpha)\hbar\nu_0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.2)$$

Now by comparing those wonderful discoveries by the elite of scientists in the past century, and the new primordial coupling series, derived mathematically in 2021, we can discover wonderful intersections. In particular, in the first and second representations of the series. Bosons as net curvature on the matrix tensor (1.3) to (1.32) and the prime critical line (1.33) to (1.35).

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.3)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.31)$$

$$N_V = 2\left(V + \frac{1}{2}\right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.32)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.33)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.34)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.35)$$

Examining the coupling term of Electromagnetism, as it was the subject Plank and Einstein worked on:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.36)$$

First point of intersection, the photon is a discrete quantity which associated with a discrete number $N_V = (+5)$ the coupling series would not be correct if it was any other number. That is synonymous with the idea behind the Plank constant. Second, since all the prime amount of curvature are associated with the prime critical line, located on one-half, which is the second point of intersection and in agreement with the discovery of Stern and Einstein. In the 8T, we can analyze the term one-half in two ways. The first, The quantum oscillator can change by prime amounts belong to the primes. The second, prime amounts will be emitted from the electron, which is itself the one- half or the majestic (3) located on one half. Those points of agreement solidify the validity of the series.

References

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- [2] O. Manor. "Fermion Clusters and Bosonic Ripples" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "The Principle of Least Variation of Lorentz Manifolds" In: (2021)